

GA 21NRM02 - Digital-IT

D6 - Collection of documents describing the outputs of the project in terms of data, methods, guidelines and recommendations, which are necessary for the calibration of SV enabled substation equipment, and email confirmation of their dissemination to IEC TC 38

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable: RISE

Due date of the deliverable: August 2025

Actual submission date of the deliverable: October 2025

Confidentiality Status: Public, fully open

Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Table of Contents

1	Summary	3
2	Publications.....	4
3	Project deliverables and good practice guides	4
4	Good news stories	4
5	Stakeholder workshops.....	4
6	Presentations at IEC TC38 meetings	4

Annex 1 - Confirmation email from IEC TC38 chair

1 Summary

This document outlines the development of several reference devices used for the calibration of Stand-Alone Merging Units (SAMUs) that are used in the electricity grid. The ongoing transformation of the grid, driven by the integration of renewable energy sources, necessitates the use of SAMUs for further control and automation of the electricity grid. However, there are currently no services available to calibrate these merging units, and the lack of dedicated reference equipment hinders progress. Reliable calibration and testing starts with traceability (derived) from National Metrology Institute (NMI) level. Accredited test and calibration laboratories need verification of the accuracy of their equipment from an NMI. The focus is on the reference devices used in calibration facilities and their technical requirements for magnitude and timing accuracy evaluation. Other aspects like latency of goose messaging and synchronization problems are not part of this project. The document identifies key substation devices that can be calibrated using a reference SAMU, including other merging units, non-conventional instrument transformers, and test bridges.

All listed documents are available for download at <https://zenodo.org/communities/digital-it>. Additional papers have been submitted, or are under preparation; they will be added later.

2 Publications

Lossless and Stateless Compression of IEC 61850 Sampled Values Flows, Newsletters,
<https://zenodo.org/records/10629711>

Metrology for digital substation instrumentation (Digital-IT), <https://zenodo.org/records/14012333>

Calibration of "PTPv2 Golden Calibrator Pair" in a distributed timing network,
<https://zenodo.org/records/15688094>

A High-Precision and Low-Complexity Framework for Calibration of Stand-Alone Merging Units,
<https://zenodo.org/records/16674080>

Design and compatibility of different Stand-Alone Merging Unit (SAMU) calibration testbeds,
<https://zenodo.org/records/17063170>

Calibration of digital energy meters with IEC 61850-9-2 inputs, <https://zenodo.org/records/17130974>

3 Project deliverables and good practice guides

D1 - Report on the realisation of a reference SAMU with up to 96 kSPS sampling rate and up to c. 40 kHz bandwidth, <https://zenodo.org/records/17176515>

D2 - **Good practice guide** on the calibration of commercial SV enabled instrumentation with sampling rates up to 96 kSPS Organisation, <https://zenodo.org/records/17177767>

D3 - Report on existing and new algorithms with their corresponding uncertainty estimation, including a software system for controlling, handling and processing SV data streams for sampling rates up to 96 kSa/s, <https://zenodo.org/records/17177799>

D4 - **Good practice guide** for the calibration of digital substation instrumentation using PTPv2 timing, <https://zenodo.org/records/17348732>

4 Good news stories

[Presentations from metrology for digital substations workshop now available](#)

[World first calibration service will support the use of renewable energy resources](#)

[Metrology for digital substation instrumentation](#)

5 Stakeholder workshops

December 2023, jointly with industry funded DigIT project, *Measurements and metering in digital substations*, [Presentations and recordings 2023](#)

Sept 2025, presentation of Digital-IT outcomes, *Workshop on measurements in digital substations*, [Presentations and recordings 2025](#)

6 Presentations at IEC TC38 meetings

October 2023, Workshop & plenary meeting:

- "IED phase traceability under PTPv2 sync"

October 2025, Plenary meeting:

- "EURAMET research project 21NRM02 Digital-IT - Metrology for digital substation instrumentation"

Hällström Jari

From: ...
Sent: 2025-10-23 17:55
To: Hällström Jari; ...
Subject: TR: Digital-IT project - collection of documents for TC38
Attachments: D6_Report - 2025-10-22.pdf

Dear Jari,
I confirm reception of this document on behalf of IEC TC 38.

... : could you officially circulate this document as INF document among TC 38?
... : could you upload the document to an appropriate folder in the WG 47 CP space ?

Best regards

...
- as IEC TC38 chair-

De : Hällström Jari ...
Envoyé : jeudi 23 octobre 2025 09:58
À : ...
Objet : Digital-IT project - collection of documents for TC38

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Dear ...,

Our three-year EU project “Metrology for digital substation instrumentation (Digital-IT)” ended in August, and we are now finalizing the reporting.

One of the required deliverables has a long name:
“Collection of documents describing the outputs of the project in terms of data, methods, guidelines and recommendations, which are necessary for the calibration of SV enabled substation equipment, and

email confirmation of their dissemination to IEC TC 38”

The deliverable is attached, and I hope you can confirm that you have received it by replying to this e-mail. Any comments are of course also welcome.

Yours, Jari

Jari Hällström

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